

EFFECTS OF INTEGRATING INDIGENOUS KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES ON POST-BASIC SCHOOL STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE IN PHYSICS IN TARABA STATE, NIGERIA

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14976544>

ABSTRACT

The study explored the effect of integrating indigenous knowledge into teaching of Physics on the academic performance of post-basic students in Taraba State, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental design with pre-test, post-test, and non-equivalent control groups was employed. The population comprised 14,495 PBS-II Physics students (8,395 males and 6,100 females) from public schools in the state. A sample of 175 students (88 males, 87 females) from four purposively selected schools was divided into experimental (97) and control (78) groups. The experimental group was taught Physics topics projectiles, equilibrium of bodies in liquid, and energy using indigenous knowledge, while the control group used conventional methods. Data were collected using a Physics Performance Test (PPT) adapted from WASSCE and NECO questions (2013–2022) and analyzed using mean, standard deviation, t-test and ANCOVA. Results revealed that students taught using indigenous knowledge performed significantly better [$F(1, 174) = 19.518, p = 0.000$]. Males outperformed females, with mean scores of 47.21 and 41.67, respectively ($p = 0.049$). No significant interaction effects were found between teaching method and gender [$F(1, 174) = 1.622, p = 0.205$]. The study recommends among others teacher training on integrating indigenous knowledge into teaching of Physics.

Keywords: Indigenous Knowledge, Practice, Gender, Academic Performance

INTRODUCTION

The advancement of any nation is closely linked to its achievements in science education, which drives technological growth, social progress, and economic development. Physics, as a cornerstone of science, plays a crucial role in wealth creation, improving quality of life, and facilitating economic transformation (Nwankwo, 2021; Chima, 2021). Developed nations have attained their status by investing in quality Physics education, encouraging research, and stimulating interest in the field (Nebo, 2017). In Nigeria, Physics education is foundational at the post-basic level, forming a critical part of the curriculum. This subject equips students with essential scientific knowledge, fosters problem-solving skills, and nurtures scientific attitudes, all of which contribute to national development (Chima, 2021). As a gateway subject for science-related courses in higher education, Physics is vital for understanding natural phenomena and driving technological advancements (Anaeto et al., 2016). However, in Taraba State, students face numerous challenges in Physics education. An analysis of WAEC results over 11 years reveals a low average credit pass rate of 25.58%, which highlights systemic issues such as

outdated resources, inadequate laboratory facilities, and uninspiring teaching methods (Sa'ad, Adamu & Abdullahi, 2014). Additionally, the perceived difficulty of the subject and limited alignment with students' cultural contexts further hinders engagement and achievement.

Integrating indigenous knowledge into Physics education offers a promising approach to addressing these challenges by contextualizing concepts within students' everyday experiences. Traditional practices like blacksmithing, pottery, and canoe crafting naturally illustrate Physics principles such as heat transfer, buoyancy, and streamlining (Ndangwa, 2017). This approach aligns with Brunner's discovery learning theory, which emphasizes linking concepts to familiar surroundings for better understanding (Childs, 2015). Ethno-Physics strategies incorporate cultural examples and traditional tools into the curriculum, fostering hands-on learning and critical thinking (Adekunle, 2017; McCausland, 2020).

Conventional teaching methods in African science education often exclude indigenous knowledge, leading to an imbalance in learning and undermining the value of local resources (Mishack, Fidelis & Anamezie, 2021). This exclusion perpetuates gender stereotypes and limits inclusivity in Physics education (Steinmayr, 2014). Integrating indigenous practices can address these issues by making Physics more relatable and creating equitable learning opportunities. Persistent stereotypes that suggest male students outperform females in Physics can also be challenged through inclusive, culturally relevant strategies (Josiah & Etukiren, 2014; Adigun et al., 2015).

Ethno-Physics teaching strategies connect students' cultural experiences with Physics concepts, creating an inclusive and engaging learning environment (Sithole, 2021). By blending indigenous practices with modern digital tools, educators can develop frameworks that bridge traditional and contemporary knowledge, fostering critical thinking, sustainability, and cultural pride (Snively & Williams, 2016). While global research supports the integration of indigenous knowledge into science education, its application in Taraba State remains limited. The region's reliance on conventional methods and resource constraints underscores the need for innovative strategies to enhance Physics education. This study investigates the effect of integrating indigenous knowledge and practices on male and female post-basic school students' academic performance in Physics in Taraba State. The findings aim to inform strategies for improving student outcomes, fostering inclusivity, and supporting broader educational and societal development goals.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The declining academic performance in Physics among Post Basic School II students in Taraba State, particularly in external examinations like WAEC and NECO, has become a significant concern. Contributing factors include the low quality of Physics teachers, with deficiencies in subject knowledge, communication skills, and attitudes (Okoronka & Wada, 2014), as well as inadequate teaching resources, such as outdated methods and insufficient facilities. Additionally, the challenging nature of Physics, with its abstract, experimental, theoretical, mathematical, and conceptual components, poses a barrier to student success (Taangahar Fatoki & Joshua, 2021). Students' lack of interest and cultural influences further complicate the issue. While global research on integrating indigenous knowledge into Physics teaching has been explored, studies specific to Taraba State are limited. Teachers in the region predominantly use conventional methods, but ongoing poor performance signals a need for more student-centered and culturally relevant approaches. The poor performance in Physics has far-reaching consequences, as Physics is foundational for science-related courses and technological development. Addressing these challenges is crucial to improving educational outcomes and fostering societal progress. This study aims to examine the effect of incorporating indigenous knowledge and practices into Physics instruction on the academic performance of Male and Female Post Basic School II students in Taraba State.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The specific objectives of the study are to:

1. Determine the effect of integration of indigenous knowledge and practices on Post Basic school two (PBS-II) students in Physics
2. Determine the effect of gender on academic performance of male and female Post Basic School two (PBS-II) students taught Physics with integration of indigenous knowledge and practices.
3. Determine the interaction effect of integration of indigenous knowledge and practices and gender on students' academic performance in Physics.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions are raised to guide the study:

1. What are the pre-test and post-test scores of Post Basic School two (PBS-II) students taught Physics using integration of indigenous knowledge and practices and those taught using the conventional instructional method?
2. What are the mean pre-test and post-test scores of male and female Post Basic School two (PBS-II) students taught Physics using integration of indigenous knowledge and practices?
3. What is the interaction effect of integration of indigenous knowledge and practices and gender on academic performance of students in Physics?

HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean scores (academic performance) of Post Basic School two (PBS-II) students taught Physics using integration of indigenous knowledge and practices and those taught using the conventional methods

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female of Post Basic School two (PBS-II) students taught Physics using integration of indigenous knowledge and practices

H₀₃: There is no significant interaction effect of integration of indigenous knowledge and practices and gender on students' academic performance in Physics.

LITERATURE REVIEW

This study is grounded in Ausubel's (1963) theory of meaningful learning and Vygotsky's (1978) Sociocultural Theory of Learning. Ausubel emphasizes the integration of new knowledge with existing cognitive structures, suggesting that linking indigenous practices with Physics concepts enhances understanding, relevance, and academic performance. Vygotsky highlights the role of social and cultural contexts in learning, where indigenous practices provide culturally relevant teaching, expanding students' Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD) through collaborative and scaffolded learning experiences. This aligns with promoting deeper cognitive engagement in Physics education.

Concept of Indigenous Knowledge and Practices

Indigenous knowledge encompasses cultural, environmental, and practical wisdom passed down through generations. It emphasizes harmony with nature and addresses local challenges using sustainable methods. Traditional tools like atlatls, bows, slings, and canoes can be linked to Physics concepts such as projectile motion, energy conservation, and fluid dynamics (Sithole, 2021). In Taraba State, ethnic groups like the Mumuye and Kona possess a wealth of indigenous

practices that can enrich Physics teaching by bridging theoretical concepts with real-world applications, fostering cultural sensitivity, and improving student engagement (Hamilton & Dorgu, 2015).

Integration of Indigenous Knowledge and Practices into Teaching

Integrating indigenous practices into education bridges traditional wisdom and modern science. Approaches include inclusive, exclusive, and overlapping perspectives, with the inclusive approach fostering cultural appreciation and deeper learning (Zidny, Sjoström, & Eilks, 2020). Practical applications of indigenous methods, such as projectiles and buoyancy, demonstrate Physics' relevance in everyday life, making it relatable and engaging for students (Claudio et al., 2023)

Gender and Students' Performance in Physics

Gender disparities in Physics performance stem from societal stereotypes and cultural perceptions that frame science and mathematics as male domains (Dania, 2014). Findings on gender performance are inconsistent: some studies show boys outperforming girls, while others report no significant differences. Socio-cultural norms and instructional methods influence these disparities (Yakubu, 2021). According to him, Inclusive teaching strategies and efforts to challenge stereotypes can bridge this gap, encouraging female participation in Physics education.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted the quasi-experimental design involving pre-test, post-test non-equivalent control group design. The total number of PBS-II students offering Physics in the state for the 2023/2024 session is 14,495. This population comprises of 8,395 male and 6,100 female students from public Post Basic Schools in the sixteen local government areas of the state. The sample of the study is 175 PBS-II students offering Physics. The study adopted a simple random sampling technique to select Jalingo zone out of the 10 education zones in the state. The instrument known as Physics Performance Test (PPT) was adapted from WASSCE and NECO from 2013-2022 questions by the researcher. The instrument consists of 50 multi-choice items with 4 options (A-D). The items in the instrument was based on the selected concepts in Physics. These topics are; Projectiles, Equilibrium of bodies in liquids and Energy which was broken down into teachable weeks. The instrument (PPT) was validated by three experts. The instrument was pilot tested at Government Science Secondary School, Jalingo. The results of the pilot study was analyzed and a reliability coefficient of 0.83 using Kuder-Richardson-20 was obtained. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while the formulated hypotheses were tested using t-test and Analysis of Co-Variance (ANCOVA) at p-value of 0.05 level of significance using SPSS.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: What are the pre-test and post-test scores of Post Basic School two (PBS-II) students taught Physics using integration of indigenous knowledge and practices and those taught using the conventional instructional method?

Table 1: Pretest and Post-test Mean Scores of Students taught Physics using Indigenous and Practices and those taught using the Conventional Instructional Method

Group	N	Pre – test		Post test		Mean Difference (Gain)
		MEAN	S.D	MEAN	S.D	
Experimental (I)	97	31.81	9.23	44.12	13.81	12.31
Control (II)	78	34.77	10.00	38.36	10.94	3.59

Table 1 above shows that the experimental group, taught using indigenous knowledge and practices, showed a higher mean gain (12.31) than the control group (3.59), indicating that integrating indigenous practices significantly enhanced learning outcomes compared to conventional methods.

Research Question 2: What are the mean pre-test and post-test scores of male and female Post Basic School two (PBS-II) students taught Physics using integration of indigenous knowledge and practices?

Table 2: Pretest and Post-test Mean Scores of Male and Female Students taught Physics using Indigenous knowledge and Practices

Teaching Methods (Treatment)	Gender	N	Pre-test Mean	S. D	Post-test Mean	S.D	Mean difference (Gain)
Indigenous Practices	M	44	33.12	8.75	47.21	14.81	14.09
	F	53	30.78	9.54	41.67	12.56	10.89

The pre-test mean scores of male and female PBS-II students taught Physics using indigenous practices were 33.12 (S.D = 8.75) and 30.78 (S.D = 9.54), respectively. Post-test mean scores were 47.21 (S.D = 14.81) for males and 41.67 (S.D = 12.56) for females, with a mean difference of 5.54 favouring male students. This indicates a higher performance gain for male students when taught using indigenous practices.

Research Question 3: What is the interaction effect of treatment and gender on academic performance of students on Physics (projectiles, equilibrium of bodies in liquid and energy)?

Figure 1: Interaction effects of Teaching Methods and Gender on Students’ Academic Performance

The graph in Figure 1 shows that there is interaction effect between teaching method and gender as shown by the two lines representing male and female but the interaction effect is not significant on students’ academic performance.

Hypotheses Testing

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean score of academic performance of Post Basic School students taught Physics using indigenous practices and those taught using the conventional methods.

Table 3: Summary of ANCOVA of Mean Scores of Students taught Physics using Indigenous knowledge and Practices and those taught using the Conventional Instructional Method

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	7412.214 ^a	4	1853.054	14.619	.000	.256
Intercept	6096.000	1	6096.000	48.091	.000	.221
Pretest	4937.886	1	4937.886	38.955	.000	.186
Teaching methods	2474.061	1	2474.061	19.518	.000	.103
Gender	153.900	1	153.900	1.214	.272	.007
Teaching methods * gender	205.646	1	205.646	1.622	.205	.009
Error	21549.020	170	126.759			
Total	331144.000	175				
Corrected Total	28961.234	174				

a. R Squared = .256 (Adjusted R Squared = .238)

Analysis in Table 3 presented summary of ANCOVA conducted to test whether significant difference exist between the mean performance scores of students taught Physics using indigenous practices and those taught using the conventional methods. The results show that there is significant difference between the performance scores of students taught Physics using indigenous practices and those taught using the conventional methods, $F(1, 174) = 19.518, p < 0.05$ with small effect size as indicated by the partial Eta squared of 0.103.

Ho2: There is no significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female of Post Basic School students taught Physics using indigenous practices.

Table 4: Summary of independent Sample t – test of Mean Scores difference of Male and Female Students taught Physics using Indigenous Knowledge and Practices

Gender	N	Mean	S. D	Df	t-value	p-value	Remark
Male	43	47.2093	14.80759	95	1.994	0.049	H ₀₂ rejected
Female	54	41.6667	12.56380				

The results of the independent sample t-test presented in Table 4 showed that the mean score for male students ($M = 47.21, SD = 14.81$) was higher than that of female students ($M = 41.67, SD = 12.56$). The t-value was 1.994, with 95 degrees of freedom, and the p-value was 0.049, which is less than the typical significance level of 0.05. Based on these results, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating that there was a significant difference in the mean academic performance scores of male and female students. The results suggest that male students performed better than female students when taught using indigenous knowledge and practices for Physics.

Ho3: There is no significant interaction effect of integration of indigenous knowledge and practices and gender on students' academic performance in Physics.

Table 5: Summary of ANCOVA of Interaction Effect of Integration of Indigenous knowledge and Practices and Gender on Students' Academic Performance in Physics.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Partial Eta Squared
Corrected Model	7412.214 ^a	4	1853.054	14.619	.000	.256
Intercept	6096.000	1	6096.000	48.091	.000	.221
Pretest	4937.886	1	4937.886	38.955	.000	.186
Teaching methods	2474.061	1	2474.061	19.518	.000	.103
Gender	153.900	1	153.900	1.214	.272	.007
Teaching methods * gender	205.646	1	205.646	1.622	.205	.009
Error	21549.020	170	126.759			
Total	331144.000	175				
Corrected Total	28961.234	174				

a. R Squared = .256 (Adjusted R Squared = .238)

Analysis in Table 5 presented summary of ANCOVA conducted to test whether there is significant interaction effect of integration of indigenous knowledge and practices and gender on students' academic performance in Physics. The results show that there is no significant interaction effect of integration of indigenous knowledge and practices and gender on students' academic performance in Physics, $F(1, 174) = 1.622, p > 0.05$ ($p = 0.205$), with very small effect size as indicated by the partial Eta squared of 0.009.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Findings with respect to research question one showed that students taught Physics concepts using indigenous knowledge and practices performed significantly better than those taught with conventional methods. This supports findings by Mbaegbu and Osuafor (2023) highlighting improved performance in science subjects through the integration of indigenous perspectives. It also aligns with Ausubel's theory of meaningful learning, which emphasizes linking new concepts with prior knowledge.

Findings with respect to research question two showed that male students outperformed females in both pre-test and post-test results, aligning with Yakubu (2021) but contradicting studies like Nnamani and Oyibe (2016), which found better performance among females, and others (e.g., Adebayo et al., 2018) reporting no significant gender influence.

Findings with respect to research question three revealed no interaction effect between teaching method and gender on academic performance, consistent with Ugwu and Diovu (2016) but differing from Ozofor and Onos (2018), who reported a significant interaction effect. These findings highlight the need for Physics teachers to adopt inclusive methods, integrating indigenous practices to enhance academic performance across genders.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that incorporating indigenous knowledge and practices into the teaching of Physics significantly enhances students' academic performance compared to conventional teaching methods in Taraba State. Furthermore, male students demonstrated higher performance scores than their female counterparts when taught

using indigenous knowledge and practices. However, the study also concludes that there is no significant interaction effect between the teaching method and gender on students' academic performance, indicating that the effectiveness of indigenous knowledge and practices in improving academic outcomes is not influenced by gender.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. It is recommended that the Taraba state government and other stakeholders should organize teacher's workshop (s) on yearly basis to train Physics teachers on how to implement indigenous practices into Physics teaching.
2. It is also recommended that Physics teachers should use approaches that will interest and encourage both genders in their academic performance.
3. It is also recommended that teachers should use appropriate resources and strategies that will engage both learners irrespective of gender differences.

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